

SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE AND ACADEMIC DISHONESTY: THE MALAYSIAN HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENT PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract:

Academic dishonesty becoming a threat to the academic world across the globe. Most studies focus on students of higher learning, but very less research focusing on Muslim students generally. Therefore, this study will examine the empirical and critical phenomena of academic dishonesty in the context of Muslim students in Malaysia. This research proposed a framework based on modified Theory of Planned Behavior by including Spiritual Intelligence as an additional predictor. The study employs quantitative method bases on survey strategy through questionnaires. The study is also based on primary data collected from 300 Muslim students in a selected public University in Malaysia. The study extended the previous study conducted the same discussion using convenience sampling. The Spiritual intelligence represented additional independent variables instead attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavior while behavior intention represented the dependent variable. In this study, the relationship had been analyzed using Smart-PLS 2.0 Beta. Two measured variables (attitude and spiritual intelligence) found a positive relationship between intentions to cheat among Malaysian Muslim students. However implication for stakeholder, educators and higher education's policy maker are discussed, and suggestions for further research are proposed.

Keywords: scientific attitude, virtual reality, hybrid learning, chemical bonding

1. Introduction

Academic dishonesty is becoming a challenge and threatening the integrity of the academic world. It is becoming a serious issue and increasing significantly (Teixeira dan Rocha, 2010; Kalhori, 2014). At the higher learning, fear towards this issue is being focused as it is increasing from time to time (Hsiao dan Yang, 2011). Donald Mc Cabe

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(2005) in his report states that about 70% higher learning students will do academic dishonesty at least once in their studies. Lin & Wen (2007) in their research towards 2,068 university students reported academic dishonesty rate is high with the ratio 61.7% which phenomena occurred among the university students in Asia especially in Taiwan. Meanwhile Tamara & Eric, (2006) reported that 80% to 90% university students has admitted ever copying, cheating and performing academic dishonesty in their studies. More suprising Demoeva & Jindrova (2013) reported that *The Center for Academic Integrity (CAI)* in their study found out that over 75% of higher learning students performed academic dishonesty at least once in their studies. Questionnaire done by *The Josephian Institutes of Ethics in California* found that 72% of higher learning students admitted performing academic dishonesty such as copying in the exam etc. (Koul, 2012).

This issue does not only becoming a threat in academic only, but portraying the students' ethic and moral nowadays. The study by Hsiao & Yang (2011) discovered unethical professional behaviour is related significantly with the tendency or intention in performing academic dishonesty among college and university students. Based on this issue, this research will contribute on the hollowness of spiritual aspect by studying the influence between spiritual intelligence towards intention in performing academic dishonesty among Muslim university students in the context of higher learning in Malaysia. Therefore, researcher will study the spiritual intelligence in general and what is its effect towards academic dishonesty issues. Systematic behaviorist theory is the basis in forming the research hypothesis and research model.

1.1 Academic dishonesty in the context of higher learning in Malaysia

In going towards developing country, Malaysia needs to spearhead the academic development competing with other countries. Issues pertaining to academic dishonesty should be seriously viewed so that the country development will be on par with the rapid academic development with integrity. Academic dishonesty issues begin to be focused when it is raised in parliament session on 26 October 2009 (Harris, 2011). In the report he stated that plagiarism issues are wide spreading in the academic world after an academicians in a university is found plagiarizing in his writings. Newspaper report in the Sun dated 13 September 2009 (Quah, Stewart & Lee, 2012) stated a professor holding a doctorate degree is under suspicion of plagiarizing several information from University Harvard and Albion College in America in his book. Investigation shows about 64 printed pages similar to the information in the university website. Other than that, one professor from an Islamic University in Malaysia was found plagiarizing in his written article (Moten, 2014).

In the context of higher learning in Malaysia too is not an exception, academic dishonesty activity occurred among university students. Nurshiha & Nurliyana (2013) Report found that 82% university students had performed academic dishonesty. Result findings from Ramlan, Zaharah dan Saedah (2016) on university students found that 62% Muslim university students admitted performing academic dishonesty in 2015 and 56% admitted performing academic dishonesty in 2014. Likewise with research on

several universities, Ibrahim, Hussein, Samat and Daud (2013) found many students performed academic dishonesty in their studies. Latisha & Surina research (2012) on 100 diploma students in the public university in Malaysia found that many students understood and knew the law institution on academic cheating issues. Research stated that influence and peer pressure together with collective culture gave direct impact on academic cheating in Malaysian public universities.

1.2 Academic dishonesty and Spiritual Intelligence

Academic dishonesty is recognized as a digressed and immoral behaviour that sullied the self-worth and integrity of one performing it. In the academic world, this topic is becoming a trend and being viral (Reisenweitz, 2012). There are many factors which push students to be involved in this academic dishonesty such as failure, desire for a high grade, external pressure, low self efficacy, competitive and lots of workload (Hassan & Ogunmakin, 2010; Okusuade & Oluwatayo, 2011). However, many researcher state aspects such as spirituality and religion play an important role in leading someone performing dishonesty and digressing behaviour (Bloodgood, 2008). This is explained based on inner individual act and self-spiritual consideration that lead human behaviour, if spiritual consideration is the behaviour core thus negative things won't happen (Bruggerman & Hart, 1996).

There are also researchers who relate the behavior of academic dishonesty with intelligence factors. Hasan & Ogunmakin (2010) attributing academic dishonesty to emotional intelligence factors. His research found that emotional intelligence had a significant impact on predicting behavior of academic dishonesty. The findings of this study are supported by the findings of Osakuade & Aluwatoyo (2011) which found that emotional intelligence factors had a positive influence on academic dishonesty. In addition, such researchers Olasula, Ajayi & Samson (2015) linking this phenomenon with moral intelligence (moral intelligence). Their study found that behaviors like deceit and dishonesty have a positive relationship with the individual's moral values and intelligence. Someone will behave badly or deviate if their moral values are at a low level.

Based on issues related to spirituality and intelligence that tried by some previous researchers, the researchers will examine aspects of spiritual intelligence and their relationship with the intention of conducting academic dishonesty behavior. At the same time, the gap is seen to be significant and suggestions from previous researchers such as (Bloodgood, 2007; Reisenwitz, 2011; Osakuade & Oluwatayo, 2011 dan Unusual et al, 2015). Which suggests that aspects of spiritual intelligence are examined more specifically and see the potential of this variable as one of the factors that may contribute to academic dishonesty? Therefore, this study will see the influence of spiritual intelligence on the intention of conducting academic dishonesty among Muslim students.

1.3 Islam and academic dishonesty

Islam basically prohibits and prohibits all forms of treatment that lead to accidents, fraud and damages. Reflect on the basis of morals and beliefs of all forms of dishonesty of unacceptable treatment in Islam. Islam views all deviations such as academic or more dishonest behavior such as plagiarism, imitation, plagiarism and others as being out of Islamic values and etiquette. Contemporary scholars, agree that imitation is fraud, and fraud is illegal in terms of *syarak*.

As prophet Muhammad S. A. W. said:

“On one day the Prophet S. A. W. had been through a man who was selling food (grain). He admired her so much, and then put her hand into the dish, when she saw that the food was wet, she asked: What does this foodman do. Then the man replied that the food was hit by rain. Then the Messenger of Allah S.A.W. He said “Why do not you put the wet above, so that others will know it?” Whosoever deceives, they are not of us (Islam)”.

(Muslim, 1/99)

Islam cursed and denounced the deviant and outrageous act of the true ethics of Islam. Deviant acts such as imitating, plagiarizing the rights of others, taking unauthorized material, falsifying sources and materials are deemed to be an act that does not conform to Islamic values (Moten, 2014). Islam also condemns violently the individuals involved with fraud or in the treatment or writing, verbal and behavioral. As Allah said:

“Do not think that those who rejoice in what they have done and who are praised by what they do not do, never think that they will be saved from punishment and they will there is a painful doom.”

(Al Imran: 188)

This verse explains that all the forms of fraud and whoever commits deeds and desires to receive the rewards and advantages of any form which he does not do then he is cursed and will get a heavy reward in the sight of Allah.

2. Literature Review

Increased academic dishonesty activity is very significant in the context of higher education today (Lewellyn & Rodriguez, 2015; Jurdi, Hage & Chow, 2011). While Lewellyn & Rodriguez, (2015) reported the American academic dishonesty rate in the 1960s at 39%, and dramatically increased in 1993 at 64%. Olafson, Schraw, Nadelson, Nadelson & Kehrwald (2013) reported in his research showing the present level of dishonesty is high at 54.1% to 70.4%. Meanwhile in Simkin & McLeod (2010) found that academic dishonesty rates are at 60% to 86%. Other relevant studies show that aspects of internet technology have had an impact on the improvement of the problem of academic dishonesty. Jones (2011) conducted a study of 48 students, revealed that there

were 3 reasons that led to this problem are grade (92%), did not have enough time to complete the task (75%).

Activities involving academic dishonesty among Muslim students are increasingly being reported (Vlaardingerbroek, Shehab and Alameh, 2011). Vlaardingerbroek et al. (2011) of 1401 university students in Lebanon showed that 59% of students did academic dishonesty in national level examinations. The study conducted by Hadijah, Norashikin, Nusrah & Fauziah (2013) against 610 students at a public university found that dishonesty was due to the fact that lecturers did not warn students about the ethics of this mistake. The findings also show the factors of irrelevance to the subject being taught as well as peer influence between the causes of this academic dishonesty.

Increasing the case the academic dishonesty is increasingly affecting educational institutions around the world and is no exception in Malaysia. According to Chuah, Stewart & Lee (2012) Academic Integrity Center report increased activity involving academic dishonesty through internet sources increased drastically. Nurshiha & Nurliyana (2013) recorded that over 82% of students are involved with academic dishonesty activities in a public university in Malaysia. An increase from time to time is seen in the context of education in Malaysia. Comparative studies conducted by Ramlan, Zaharah & Saedah (2016) indicating an increase in the percentage of academic dishonesty that 55% of Muslim students are involved with academic dishonesty in 2014 and 63% of students involved in the following year.

3. Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991)

The Theory of Planned Behavioral, founded by (Ajzen, 1991) is a very significant behavioral psychology model in a study based on the aspects of human behavioral intentions. The Theory of Planned Behavioral is able to predict well aspirations or intentions to behave. (Hsiao & Yang, 2011; Harding, Mayheaw, Finelli & Carpenter, 2007). This theory is a connection to the Theory of Reason Actions founded by Ajzen (1971) widely used in predicting and explaining human behavior in various fields of study. Based on this theory, human behavior will act in the intention of an act that becomes a proxy for the occurrence of a behavior.

The Planned Behavioral Theory has three main variables: attitudes, subjective norms and control of behavior. The first variable of attitude is a reflective act on the desire of a person's feelings whether good or bad about an action (Hsiao et al, 2011; Ajzen, 1991). The second variable of subjective norm refers to the influence of the environment or the social (family, siblings, friends etc.) that affects the actions of an individual in behavior (Ajzen, 1991; Harding et al, 2007; Hsiao et al, 2011 dan Alleyne & Philip, 2011). While the third variable of the theory is to know behavior that also plays an important role in this theory. Knowing behavior is a reaction or reflective of past experiences, obstacles, opportunities, times, abilities and skills capable of controlling the behavior of an individual (Stone, Jawahar & Kisamore, 2010; Ajzen, 1991; Harding et al, 2007; Hsiao et al, 2011 dan Alleyne & Philip, 2011). TPB has become a directed and

dominant theory in the study involving academic dishonesty. This is based on the findings.

This is based on the findings (Whitley, 1998; Harding, Mayhew & Carpenter, 2007) which conducts a meta-analysis study proving that all TPB variables support as a specific theory in describing the phenomenon of academic dishonesty. According to Whitley (1998) students with good attitudes are more likely not to do anything that is deviant compared with students who have the opposite attitude. In addition, students with strong influence environments such as family, friends and others will tend to deviate behavior based on the influence of subjective norms (environmental influences) and students who have high levels of self-esteem and self-esteem capable of self-restraint in the abandonment of such an academic dishonesty (perceived behavior control). This theory is also supported by Ajzen (1991) which states that this theory is the right theory in predicting the behavior of academic dishonesty and cheating in academics.

Therefore, this study will use the intention as a dependent variable in addition to the three main independent variables: attitudes, subjective norms and control of behavior and the addition variable are spiritual intelligence. This study will relatively examine the influence of additional variables which may affect the intent to commit academic dishonesty within the scope of Muslim students in Malaysia.

3.1 Research framework

Based on the findings of the study, researchers use Ajzen 1991's planned behavioral theory as the basic theory of study and the addition of aspects of spiritual intelligence in studying the relationship between variables with the intention of conducting academic dishonesty among Muslim students. There are several studies that examine the relationship between intelligence factors but the aspect of spiritual intelligence in the Islamic model has never been studied. Therefore the researcher tried to fulfill this gap

Figure 1: Research Model

Based on the theory chosen by the literature of this study, it shows a positive relationship between the student and the intention to do academic dishonesty. This study assumes that there is a positive relationship between attitude elements, subjective norms, know-how behavior and spiritual intelligence. Therefore we assume:

Ha1: There was a significant positive relationship between attitudes toward the intent to commit academic dishonesty among Muslim students.

Ha2: There was a significant positive relationship between the subjective norms of intent to commit academic dishonesty among Muslim students.

Ha3: There is a significant positive relationship between knowing behavior toward the intention to commit academic dishonesty among Muslim students

Ha4: There is a significant positive relationship between spiritual intelligence and the intention to commit academic dishonesty among Muslim students.

4. Material and Methods

Basically, this study uses quantitative methods in questionnaire. This study is based on a combination approach between descriptive, inferential and correlational (Frankeal, Wallen & Hyun, 2011). According to Mohd Majid Konting (2004), the design of the study is a specific technique and methodology to obtain the information needed to solve the problem. The design of this study is based on a quantitative approach in the form of surveys. The survey method is used in this study as there are advantages which are the method of collecting direct answers from the subjects of the study, the data can be collected quickly and the ability of the results of the study to generalize the population accurately and effectively (Chua Yan Piaw, 2006). The survey method is also useful for measuring opinions, attitudes and behaviors (Kothari, 2012). In addition, its use is also intended to pay attention to the description, explanation and exploration of the subjects (Babbie, 1998).

4.1 Sampling procedure

The sample of the study consists of 300 Muslim students from 3 public universities in Malaysia. Samples were selected using the simple sampling method (Convenience sampling). Although this sampling cannot be generalized in general, the findings of the study are necessarily non probability is the best method to employ if the researcher does not have a sampling framework (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010; Malhotra, 1999). The population (target population) of the study consists of undergraduate degree students from various faculties.

4.2 Instrumentation

The instrument used in this study is a questionnaire. The questionnaire form has been designed based on previous studies. Instruments to measure the construct of organized by Theory Of Planned behavioral (TPB) such as attitude, subjective norms, perceived behavior control and intentions will be measured using instruments used by Stones, Jawahar & Kisamore (2010) that adapted the Ajzen instrument (2002) and (Armitage & Corner, 2001). While the Instrument of spiritual intelligence adapted from Jumahat, Bensaid & Nordin (2014).

4.3 Data analysis

This study uses statistical methods using Partial Least Square (PLS-SEM) version 2.0 beta. The model of the study was empirically measured using the Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method based on the structural model construction method, the appropriate method was VB SEM (variance based SEM) (Hair, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2014)

4.4 Data screening procedure

Before conducting an analysis of the measurement model and the structural model we conducted an analysis of procedures for data loss and remote data. The results of the analysis found that there were 4 missing data. We use Estimation Maximization (EM) method by using SPSS version 20 to analyze lost data and so on. This method is chosen because it is more accurate and consistent than the list-waist deletion method (Ramayah, Lee & Lim, 2012; Graham, Hofer, Donaldson, McKinnon & Schaffer, 1997). In addition, remote data analysis was conducted and there were 4 remote data cases recorded. We use the case wise diagnostic method to analyze the data of the findings of the four data being discarded so as not to impair data analysis

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Respondent background

Respondents of this study consist of 296 Muslim undergraduate students from three public universities in Malaysia. A complete analysis of the respondents' profile is shown in the following table:

Table 1: Demography (n= 296)

Gender	Number	Percents
Male	138	46.6
Female	158	53.4

A total of 296 respondents comprising Muslim undergraduate students who are studying in various fields of study. Table 1 shows the data distribution of respondents based on gender. 46.6% of respondents are males while 53.4% of respondents are females.

Table 2: Field of study (n= 296)

Gender	Number	Percents
Education	83	27.6
Language	64	21.3
Economic	86	28.6
Engineering	67	22.3

Table 2 shows the areas of study of respondents involved in the study. A total of 83 respondents were from Faculty of Education students representing 27.6%. In addition, a total of 64 (21.3%) students from the Faculty of Languages, 86 (28.6%) of the Faculty of

Economics and 67 (22.3%) of the Faculty of Engineering are students of the Faculty of Engineering.

5.2 Measurement Model

5.2.1 Convergent Validity

Table 3: Measurement model (loading factor, AVE, composite reliability & Cronbach Alpha)

Construct	Item	Loading	AVE	Composite reliability	Cronbach alpha
Attitude	Att1	0.980	0.913	0.876	0.808
	Att2	0.954			
	Att3	0.952			
	Att4	0.936			
Subjective norm	Norm1	0.873	0.787	0.856	0.909
	Norm2	0.929			
	Norm3	0.913			
	Norm4	0.830			
Perceived behaviour control	Pbc1	0.951	0.815	0.746	0.831
	Pbc2	0.879			
	Pbc3	0.860			
	Pbc4	0.917			
Spiritual intelligence	SQ1	0.965	0.823	0.865	0.856
	SQ2	0.768			
	SQ3	0.923			
	SQ4	0.928			
	SQ5	0.916			
	SQ6	0.927			
Intention	Int1	0.969	0.886	0.918	0.836
	Int2	0.941			
	Int3	0.940			
	Int4	0.912			

To determine the validity of the measurement model (CFA) in Smart PLS, some items such as loading items, AVE, and Composite Reliability need to be accessed using PLS algorithm (as in table 3). In this study, the researcher conducted a convergent validation test on the instrument. The method used to test the validity of convergence is to measure the value of AVE (average variance extracted) as suggested by Fornell and Larcker (1981). In addition to the AVE values, convergence validity is also evaluated through composite reliability values. If the value of composite reliability exceeds 0.7 (Nunally and Bernstein, 1994), then the instrument of study reaches the validity standard of convergence. Furthermore, the factor of load factor exceeding 0.7 also proves that the instrument of this study achieves convergent validity standards (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). In this study, the researcher examines loading factor and composite reliability as well as average variant extracted. According to Table 1, all loading items

exceeding the value of 0.7, they have a good value (Hair et al., 2013; Fornell et al, 1981) except 2 items in the spiritual intelligence construct below the threshold value of 0.7, and then it is dropped. While the AVE value also exceeds the threshold value (0.5) as suggested (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

A. Discriminant Validity

Table 4: Correlation matrix among latent variable

	Attitude	Intention	Subjective norm	Perceived behavior control	Spiritual intelligence
Attitude	0.955				
Intention	0.807	0.841			
Subjective norm	0.696	0.648	0.887		
Perceived behaviour control	-0.027	0.088	-0.095	0.902	
Spiritual intelligence	0.803	0.782	0.654	0.092	0.907

In addition, convergent validity is measured by square root of average variance extracted. As shown in table 4, the square root of AVE value, as shown in bold for each construct, shows the value greater than the value of the correlation with the other constructs, confirming that there is a constricton of construct validity.

Table 5: Cross Loading

Item	Attitude	Intention	Subjective norm	Perceived behavior control	Spiritual intelligence
att1	0.980	0.809	0.698	-0.037	0.805
att2	0.954	0.783	0.669	-0.001	0.781
att3	0.952	0.732	0.668	-0.013	0.734
att4	0.936	0.756	0.626	-0.050	0.748
int1	0.814	0.969	0.654	0.064	0.965
int2	0.702	0.941	0.569	0.117	0.923
int3	0.752	0.940	0.627	0.066	0.928
int4	0.768	0.912	0.588	0.085	0.916
norm1	0.625	0.595	0.873	-0.049	0.592
norm2	0.671	0.650	0.929	-0.033	0.654
norm3	0.632	0.552	0.913	-0.133	0.574
norm4	0.529	0.483	0.830	-0.141	0.482
sq1	0.814	0.769	0.654	0.064	0.965
sq10	0.524	0.704	0.473	0.120	0.768
sq2	0.702	0.641	0.569	0.117	0.923
sq3	0.752	0.940	0.627	0.066	0.928

sq4	0.768	0.912	0.588	0.085	0.916
sq5	0.781	0.903	0.635	0.060	0.927
tahu1	-0.035	0.114	-0.100	0.951	0.114
tahu2	-0.034	0.041	-0.096	0.879	0.042
tahu3	-0.054	0.024	-0.072	0.860	0.040
tahu4	0.008	0.070	-0.068	0.917	0.077

While discriminant validity refers to the discriminant level between one construct with another construct (Urbach et al., 2010). The discrimination validity test is carried out to determine whether a construct is measuring what should be measured. This study uses a cross-loading item comparison table to test the discrimination validity. This method can be implemented by correlating the items of a construct with the item from another construct (Chin, 2010). The loading value of an item needs to be higher for its constructed construct only, and low for other constructs. In conclusion the researcher explains that each item cannot be used to measure other constructs other than the constructs represented only. This study shows the value of the item reaches the level of discrimination validity standards (refer Table 3). Overall, the Measurement model or Confirmatory Factor analysis has been validated through convergent validity and discrimination validity.

B. Structural model analysis

To test the measurement model, the bootstrapping approach is used in smart PLS to determine the significant level of each construct (path modeling). Diagram 2 and Table 4 show bootstrapping results with 5000 samples as suggested by Hair et al (2014)

Figure 2: Structural model

Table 6: Hypothesis testing

	Beta β	Standard Error	T Statistics	Remark
att -> int	-0.03264	0.016035	2.0359**	Support
norm -> int	0.012415	0.009820	1.2642	Not supported
pbc -> int	0.002201	0.009956	0.22112	Not supported
sq -> int	-0.317200	0.012726	6.5497**	Support

* $p < 0.1$ ** $p < 0.05$ *** $P < 0.01$

1 tail test

The results of figure 2 and table 4 indicate that hypothesis 1 predicts that there is a significant negative relationship between attitude and intent to commit academic dishonesty. The results of the constructional analysis of attitudes towards the intention to do academic dishonesty show a significant relationship with the value of $\alpha = -0.0326$, $p < 0.05$. However, the subjective norms indicate an insignificant relationship with the value of $\alpha = 0.877$, $p < 0.01$, which does not support the predictions of hypothesis 2. For Hypothesis 3 it is predicted that the behavioral aspect of behavior toward intent to plagiarism, significant with the intention to plagiarism with the value of $\alpha = 0.0124$, $p < 0.01$. However, the spiritual intelligence variable shows a significant negative relationship with the value $\alpha = -0.3172$, $p < 0.05$. However, of these four factors, the factor of spiritual intelligence is the strongest variable or factor determining the intention to commit academic dishonesty among Malaysian Muslim students. The results of the analysis also show that two hypotheses in this study support the hypothesis of the study with the value of T (t-value) between 2.0359 to 6.597.

C. Predictive relevant (Q2) dan Predictive power (R2)

In this study, we specifically set 500 re-sampling (bootstrapping) numbers. The research model shows a predictive power of moderate value of $R^2 = 62$ for intentional variables of academic dishonesty. This means the R^2 value suggests that 62% variants can be explained between dependent variables with independent variables. In addition, we also refer to the accuracy of the Q2 predictor. We use blindfolding method to assess the accuracy of forecasting. The blindfolding analysis shows $Q^2 = .532$ and it meets the $Q^2 > 0.5$ (Hair et al, 2010; Henseler et al, 2009).

6. Recommendations

After reviewing the findings of the study and the literature review, it can be summarized and suggested some aspects as a guide:

- Development of ethical awareness among Students. This should be noted because they will be future teachers who will be educating in the future. Good ethics and moral values need to be nurtured in order for the teaching profession to demonstrate high integrity and relevant relevance. Nurshiha et.al (2013) states that the behavior of cheating and dishonesty among trainees teachers implies the

behavior of the teacher itself in the future. Lupton and Chapman (2002) and Husu and Tirri (2003) point out that academic dishonesty in the teaching profession provides a strong reflection of the teacher's future behavior. Authorities, especially institutional administrators, need to periodically carry out various aspects of ethical development and awareness among trainees, in order for the value and integrity of the teaching profession to be a bet can be left to be more relevant

- Development of religious values among students. Religious matters are significant because they affect the judgment of one's behavior. Koul (2012) in his study of 2123 high school students in Thailand using several variables such as gender, professional career aspirations combined with materialism, religion and the goal of achieving the desire to cheat. The findings show that the factors of materialism and career aspirations have a positive relationship with the desire to do academic fraud. Both of these factors have a significant value to the intent to commit fraud with values ($\alpha = .321$ and $\alpha = .167$). Meanwhile religious factors (saksana) and master goals have insignificant or negative values with intent to commit fraud with values ($\alpha = -.107$, $\alpha = -.108$). The strongest variable against the intention to commit dishonesty in this study is the factor of materialism and achievement goals. This shows that the higher the religious value the less the academic behavior among the students. Thus the development of religious values is seen as significant and necessary.

7. Conclusion

The issue of academic dishonesty is increasingly becoming a trend in today's academic world (Stone et al, 2010). This is not a shocking thing, but it has become a phenomenon in the academic world as well as the speed of technology such as the internet, social networks and so on, making this phenomenon easier. As a person who is directly involved with the academic world, this phenomenon should look deeper, identify the cause and improve the way we handle and enforce aspects to solve this problem, so that the academic world will continue to be relevant in the future. The use of software applications such as Turnitin and so on is not sufficient to curb this problem, most importantly; self-awareness, attitude and ethical values need to be emphasized in individuals.

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